

Marjona Choriyeva

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Abstract. When feminism is first introduced, a question comes up: What is feminism? Feminism is both a social and political movement which aimed at achieving social, political, and economic equality for all genders. It largely originated in the West. However, many people do not know the full history of feminism and how it can be connected to the Islamic world. For this reason, I decided to write about the history of feminism not only in the West but also in Islamic countries.

Historically, feminism began in the 19th century. The feminist movement is divided into four waves: the second wave in the 1960–1980s, the third wave in the 1990–2000s, and the fourth wave from the 2010s to the present.

How does feminism influence society?

In this article, you will find answers to questions such as: Why do we need feminism? What are the differences between Islamic and Western feminism? Which countries' women suffer the most from inequality? In addition to that, many people are against feminism, why do they think so? Also, everything has its good and bad sides. I want to highlight both perspectives in this research and explore people's opinions about feminism and why different ideas appear in people's minds. Through this, we can understand the most important aspects of feminism.

Nowadays it has become more popular not only Western countries but also Islamic world.

Key words: Islamic feminism, women's rights, society, Qur'an, Hadith, Western feminism

1. Western feminism

1.1 Now, feminism is one social movement that protects women's rights, so it began in 19th century among nations and communities but in 18th century Mary Wollstonecraft published a work in 1792 named "A Vindication of women's rights" and she was first feminist in west, so Mary Wollstonecraft argues that women are not inferior to men, they should be educated and should have same rights as men, for example to participate in public life, basically about gender equality, importance of education and equal treatment for women.

1.2 After that the first wave (late nineteenth to early twentieth century) focused on legal issues such as property, ownership, education and suffrage. The second wave

(1960s-1980s) expanded its scope to workplace equality, reproductive rights and anti-discrimination.

1.3 The third wave (1990s-2000s) emphasized diversity, sexuality, and ability alongside gender.

1.4 The fourth wave (2010s-present) uses digital technologies to address ongoing forms of gender discrimination. Additionally, feminism is often divided into two sections: one is liberal, the other is radical. Liberal feminism which argues legal equality, individual rights, and participation in existing societal structures, but when it comes to radical feminism it argues that gender inequality is deeply embedded in patriarchal structures and that societal transformation is necessary to achieve equality.

2. Islamic feminism

2.1 Islamic feminism has caused significant debate among professionals and the public. Therefore, Islamic feminism differs from Western feminism, although both Islamic and Western feminists fight against gender discrimination, rights and role of women in society. Like Western feminism, Islamic feminism also focuses on not only gender equality and social justice but also supporters of Islamic feminism believe the Qur'an and Hadith are primary source can be considered for Muslim activists. So, Islam feminists also want to equality on education and against discrimination.

2.2 Islamic feminism history.

When Islamic feminism first appeared, women have right to inherit property and early and forced marriage was disappeared and society gives right to participate in education and knowledge. So, Islam promoted moral equality among both men and women.

2.3 Men and women's spiritual equality.

When it comes to Qur'an (*Surah Al-Azhab (33:35)*) says that "Indeed, Muslim men and Muslim women, the believing men and believing women.... – for them Allah prepared forgiveness and a great reward.

3. Difference between Islamic and Western feminism

3.1 As I mentioned before, feminism is the movement for gender equality and justice which advocating women and men should have equal rights, opportunities and participation in society. However, both Islamic and Western feminism differ significantly in their approaches and philosophical frameworks, even though both share the goal of promoting women's rights. Western feminism is largely a secular movement, Enlightenment values like autonomy, reasons and universal human rights that express philosophical roots that found in secular humanism. There some other different philosophical ideas such as John Stuart Mill (1806-1873), Anna Doyle

Wheeler (1785-1848), Frances Wright (1795-1852).

3.2 Philosophical concepts

As for their ideas, John Stuart Mill argued that women should have liberty and equality under law, so he tries to reach them. Anna Doyle Wheeler American feminists and she advocates for radical improvements in women's rights. When it comes to Frances Wright advocate for women's rights and education. All of them write books, novels and ideas with Western way of thinking.

In the Islamic feminism, proponents of feminism argue women's rights within the framework of Islamic teachings. This movement maintains that gender inequality and they say that it is not from religion, but from patriarchal ideas of Islam. There also some philosophers such as Amina Wadud, Asma Barlas, Azizah al-Hibri. As for their ideas, Amina Wadud argues that women should have equality within the limits of Islam and his book named "Qur'an and Women", she mentioned equality between women and men in the Qur'an. She says that Islam is not unfair to women but unfairness comes from people not from Allah. Asma Barlas Pakistan-American writer and academic think that the Qur'an teaches moral equality of men and women and both are created from single soul.

So, both Islamic and Western feminism almost argues same ideas, only differs from their religion.

4. Why we need feminism? And how it influence society?

Feminism is not only need for women, but also need for society because it examines how society has built our ideas both moral and personal experience. There are also some philosophical ideas about that side. Now, looks at their perspectives one by one. A British philosopher Miranda Fricker who is best known for the concept of epistemic injustice which means injustice related to knowledge and understanding, also she identifies two main types of injustice. First injustice is testimonial which explained someone's words are not believed or taken seriously because of unfairness. Second is Hermeneutical injustice which means, when people lack of concepts to explain their experiences. "Without feminist perspective, many aspects of human experience remain misunderstood" said Miranda Fricker.

Furthermore, American feminists and psychologist Carol Gilligan author of "In different voice: Psychological theory and Women's development" argues that both men and women use same perspectives such as justice, care and responsibility and her research she identified two types of moral perspective which both men and women should equal.

First is justice, it includes rules, rights, laws and fairness, the second is the care perspective which focuses on context and human connection such as relationships and responsibility. From her work, she tries to help feminist ethics, especially ethics of care. Moreover, feminism is necessary not only equal rights and social justice but also complete and understanding knowledge, ethics and experience and feminism can be strengthen society's ability to pursue justice for all gender.

5. Why some people against feminism? And why they think so?

Everyone has their point of view about feminism some of them agree with that movement, but others against it because of misunderstanding and don't know real meaning of it. American philosopher Christina Hoff Sommers who critic of modern feminism and she argues about it in her book named "Who stole feminism", but she is not completely against feminism. She partly against some perspectives like always represents women as victim. An American economist and author Bryan Caplan against feministic movement and he mention about it his essay named "Don't be feminist: A letter for my daughter" for her daughter Valeria Caplan. He thinks that men spent more time on the job than women but also men are more likely to be victims of violent crime and he explain it using statistics so that he do not want his daughter to be feminist.

6. Which countries most suffer from inequality in the world? There are a lot of countries women suffer from inequality, such as Afganistan, Pakistan, Sudan, Syria, Yemen and Democratic Republic of Congo. Furthermore, based on facts Afganistan's women most suffer from inequality even they study at school no more than two years. Also this county has one of highest rates of gender violence, it shows that most women are in relationship with a violent partners. In Pakistan many women suffer extreme discrimination during their lifetime. Even girls receive less than four years of education so that child marriage is common in this country. In the Yemen women discrimination related to vulnerable female population and discriminatory legal system and economic inequality. I think some of that countries discrimination related to wars among countries even their civil war. If they stop that kind of wars they reach not only equality and justice, but also peace. In some scientific ideas says that because of long civil wars inequality and discrimination has increased widely. For other point of view that discrimination related to traditional ways, for example, in India child marriage and limited women career opportunities are common.

Philosopher Amartya Sen says that freedom depends on real opportunities, in poor countries like Niger, females leave school early because of work or young marriage. When resources are limited, surely the family invests first for boys.

7. Is Feminism only western idea?

In many people think that feminism is only related to western countries but there some reasons show that it is not only western, but also Islamic ideas. In many Islamic societies, women faced discrimination and injustice they try to solve it using religious, cultural and social way rather than copying Western feminism. For example, in Egypt in the early 20 century, feminist Huda Shaarawi criticized restriction on women's education and she find solution within Egyptian society not as a Western way. Similarly, in Pakistan argues about limited women's legal rights and engaged in legal debate and using constitutional arguments not using Western feminist language. Another example, in Malaysia and Indonesia, Muslim women's organizations like Sisters in Islam argue for gender equality within Islamic texts. These groups do not reject, they find solution using Qur'an and Hadith. Similarly, in Morocco, women's rights activists argue for rights in marriage, divorce and child custody. It depends on Islamic principles of justice, not Western pressure alone.

8. Difference between Islam and cultural customs.

In many Islamic counties, some harmful actions women are called "religious" but it is not related to Islam, it is cultural thinking about inequality and justice. For example, in Afghanistan, some women are not allowed to gain knowledge even some areas banned to go schools. In some document, it explained because of religion, however Islam encourages education both men and women. So, in some cases it related to cultural and political decision. Another example, in Pakistan girls still forced to marriage in some societies and families sometimes say religion allow this but in that case, Islam requires a women's freedom in marriage. Some feminists and scholars explained that forced marriage based on tribal traditions, not Islamic teachings. In some African countries like Somalia which is also happens similar situations and it was also proven that practices are not religious but cultural traditions.

9. History of Islamic feminism evolution.

Some people know history of Western feminism and its main section like radical and liberal feminism, but in Islamic feminism they don't know full history or some facts about it. Islamic feminism began many centuries ago, in the early Islam, women were important for society. For example, Khadijah bint Khuwaylid first wife of Prophet Muhammad which was successful businesswomen and her life show that women could be independent and respected. Another example is Aisha bint Abu Bakr, she taught that both men and women, proving that women had strong intellectual roles in early Islam

history. Philosopher Qasim Amin, in his book named “The liberation of women (1899), argued that women have rights to education and take part in public life, it shows that Islam support justice and equality. Nowadays, Islamic Feminism has become more visible because of many philosophers like Asma Barlas and Amina Wadud. They argued that the Qur’an supports gender equality when it read fairly. Amina Wadud’s book named “Qur’an and women” (1999) which explains the Qur’an from a women’s sides. Asma Barlas think that Islam supports independence and justice for all genders. In Turkey, Ataturk also gave women political and social rights, including the right to participate in public.

10. Should everyone be a feminist?

In some ideas, many people think that, if all people be a feminist, the world changed in a good way and this movement change people’s opinions about inequality, injustice and discrimination.

10.1 Her early career

There some facts about them and I explain it using one book named “We should all be Feminist” published by Nigerian writer Chimamanda Ngozi Adichie and that book is based on a TEDx talk which she gave in 2012. She was born on September 15, 1977 in Nigeria. She study 3 university the last one is Yale University and her education deeply related to gender and race issues and she has strong ability to not only storytelling but also to explain complex ideas in simple words . During her career she writes some famous works like “Purple Hibiscus” (2003), “Half of tallow sun” (2006) and “Americanah” (2013). In “We should all be feminists”, she explains meaning of feminism and why it important for everyone, not only women. She uses examples from her life and society, how gender equality affects people’s behavior. That book easy to understand feminism and encourages gender equality and also she mentioned that feminism not about hating men, it about everyone has fair chances to life. The book shows that how society treats men and women different way from their childhood and how they create unfair situations. Adichie write that women often taught to be quiet, polite and patient, while men are taught to be strong and not show their emotions. These inequality starts from their home, school and media and because of these reasons some women may avoid taking risks or faces difficulties to expressing their thoughts. Furthermore, women often face challenges at work or in relationships because of beliefs that women can or cannot do. Men also suffer from strict rules about how they should act. In her opinion, equality benefits everyone because when both gender treated fairly society becomes stronger.

10.2 Who can be feminist?

Moreover, she argues that true feminism is about freedom which is to choose, to speak, to exist equality. Feminism is not only a movement for women alone, but also for equality and justice for all. Feminism is everyday actions, for example, women work in male-dominated work like engineering for practicing equality. Another example, when a man shares household duties equally with her wife, he is supporting feminism. In addition schools also teach both males and females that they can become leaders, doctors and scientists which is also support feminism the way of gender equality. In interesting fact that in history a young girl from Pakistan, her name is Malala Yousafzai. She argues for women's rights to education and also wrote a blog for BBC when she was 11 years old and that blog she explain life under the Taliban and the importance of education for girls. Interestingly enough, she does not worry about die or does not think what happens after that movement and since today she is symbol of equality and feminism. She won the Nobel Prize in 2014 because of her movement even she was so young. There some dilemma about inequality all over the world, one of them, some people say "girls are bad at math" or "boys should not cry" even there are no facts about them and these are false and harmful ideas about genders. Feminism encourages people to understand that misunderstandings.

10.3 Feminism and society

Feminism can change society for the better but how? So with gender equality some areas change like lower poverty, education and stronger economy. When women can work, study and vote they can decrease the poverty rate.

10.4 Everyone can support feminism

People have their own different ideas about feminism, some of them positive, some of them negative, but feminists do not force people to be feminist or support feminism. If they want to support that movement, there are some ways to support it. Firstly, gender equality or feminism movement start from family and they should share household chores equally and teach their children both men and women can do anything. Second step is school because it can encourage female to participate in science and male to explore art. Likewise, at work and daily life, they can speak unfair dilemmas about gender and also respect other's choices.

11. Conclusion

In that article, we learn about Western and Islamic feminism and different

philosophical ideas about them. Feminism not only about women's right but also equality and fairness for everyone, irrespective of their gender. Islamic feminism wants equality but within Qur'an and religion, in Western feminism focuses on jobs, education, justice and equal treatment but not religious. In both sides feminism fights against unfair treatment and participate in public life. Supporting feminism is the best way, for example Malala Yousafzai who took a risk for women education and wrote blog about it and she shows that fighting for equality is important. In some cases, people against feminism because of misunderstanding and radical feminism movements. Feminism also helps society to improve their lifestyle by feminism movement and teaches children equality in every sides and also sharing responsibilities, respecting each other are small ways people can support it. That movement helps some countries especially living in poor conditions. Furthermore, feminism can help everyone not just women and it helps life fairer and society stronger. When both men and women have same rights and changes, it can change people's incorrect idea about feminism. In short, feminism is about respect, equality and justice. Feminism is helping create better world for today and future.

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